

FAILURE BEHAVIORS OF CYLINDRICAL ADHESIVE JOINTS OF GFRP UNDER COMBINED BENDING AND TORSIONAL LOADINGS

Katsuhiko Osaka and Takehito Fukuda
(Faculty of Engineering, Osaka City University
3-138, Sugimoto 3-chome, Sumiyoshi-ku, Osaka, Japan)

ABSTRACT

In this paper, the strength and the failure process of the cylindrical adhesive joints of GFRP have been investigated under combined bending and torsional loading conditions.

Experiments were performed with an apparatus capable of applying bending and torsional moments in various proportions. In these tests, three kinds of ratios of bending and torsional moments (3:2, 1:1 and 1:2) were adopted. From results of these experiments, it was found that the failure criterion of cylindrical joints of GFRP was expressed by an elliptic equation in terms of bending and torsional moments.

In order to know the extent of damage in the joint, strains and AE in this part were measured in tensile, bending, torsional and combined bending and torsional loading tests. From these results, it became clear that the failure of cylindrical adhesive joints was mainly in the adhesive layer under tensile loading, while under the other loading conditions damage was undergone in the adherent. It was also found that the damage region in the joint was characterized by the loading conditions. That is, under the bending condition the central area of the joint was mainly damaged and with increasing of ratio of the torsional moment to the bending moment, the main damage area developed and was reached to the joint end.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) have been often used as structural members. Therefore, GFRP joint structures are indispensable and their importance become greater. As adhesively bonded joints have less additional weight, they have an advantage of saving weight in comparison with mechanical fastening joints. Consequently, it is important that the failure processes under combined loading conditions are made clear not only for adhesively bonded joints of plates, but also those of cylinders. Many studies on adhesively bonded joints of plates have been performed, but a few studies on cylindrical joints have been made.¹⁾²⁾³⁾ And studies on the failure process of cylindrical joints are few.

In this study, the bending, the torsional and their combined load tests were performed for cylindrical adhesively bonded joints. From these results, the failure criterion under the combined loading condition was examined. And the failure processes of cylindrical adhesively bonded joints under the combined loading conditions were made clear with the strain and the AE measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Specimen

The cylindrical adhesively bonded joint specimen is shown in Fig. 1. The joint specimens were made up with unidirectional GFRP cylinders which were fabricated with glass roving and polyester resin in a pultrusion process. The adherents had a 27mm internal diameter, a 31mm external diameter and a length of 80mm. And the

Fig.1 Specimen geometry

Fig.2 Testing apparatus

Fig.3 Location of strain gages

Fig.4 Schematic diagram of measuring system

Fig.5 Location of AE sensors

GFRP overlay having a 31mm internal diameter, a 38mm external diameter and a 20mm length, was bonded to the adherents at the joint part with the epoxy-polyamine adhesive.

2. Experimental procedures

The tensile, the bending, the torsional and the combined bending and torsional tests were performed. In the tensile test, the specimens were loaded at a cross head speed of 3mm/min, using Instron type testing machine. The bending, the torsional and the combined load test were performed with a testing apparatus designed in our laboratory. This testing apparatus is so designed that it can be installed in the Instron type testing machine and apply the combined bending and torsional moment of which ratio can be changed. It is shown in Fig. 2. Three kinds of the combined load test in which the ratios of the bending moment to the torsional one were 3:2, 1:1 and 1:2 were carried out. In order to know the failure process from the variation of the strain near the joint, the strain measurements were performed. The strain gages were put at the joint as shown in Fig. 3. The effects of the bending and the torsional moments on the adhesive layer were measured with the strain gage put in the longitudinal direction and that put in the direction of 45°, respectively. The signals of the strain and the load were transferred to a desktop computer through an A/D converter.

And the AE signals at the joint were also measured. A measuring system is shown in Fig. 4. AE sensors were fixed at the positions shown in Fig. 5. The AE sensors were the resonance type having a resonance frequency of 140kHz. The AE parameters measured were also transferred to the desktop computer through a GP-IB interface.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Strength

The average tensile failure load of the test specimens was 8.6kN. And the average shear strength of the adhesive layer was 8.9MPa. The results of the bending, the torsional and the combined bending and torsional tests are shown in Fig. 6. An abscissa and an ordinate in the figure are the bending moment and the torsional one when the specimens failed, respectively. A mark of ● in the figure is the average strength of the experimental data.

One of the authors has reported that the following algebra expression was suitable for the failure criterion formula of thin-walled composite structures under combined bending and torsion.(4)

$$\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right) + \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_0}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

where

σ_0 = the bending strength
 τ_0 = the shear strength
 σ = the bending stress
 τ = the shear stress

In this study Eq.(2) was adopted as the failure criterion formula for the cylindrical adhesively bonded joints. Eq.(2) was made by replacing the bending strength σ_0 , the shear strength τ_0 , the bending stress σ and the shear stress τ with the bending failure moment M_0 , the torsional failure moment T_0 , the bending moment M , and the torsional moment T in Eq.(1).

$$\left(\frac{M}{M_0}\right) + \left(\frac{T}{T_0}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

The curve in Fig. 6 represents Eq.(2). There is good agreement between calculated values using Eq.(2) and experimental data. Consequently, it is also known that the failure criterion formula for GFRP cylindrical adhesively bonded joints is expressed in a simple elliptical equation in terms of bending and torsional moments.

Fig.6 Failure moments under combined bending and torsional loadings

2. Failure processes in the adhesive layer

A. Strain measurements

Variations of the load and the strain near the joint with the loading time in tensile, bending and torsional tests are shown in Figs. 7(a)-(c). Each result is one of typical examples. The strains in the tensile and the bending tests were measured in the longitudinal direction and the strain in the direction of 45° were measured in the torsional tests.

In Fig. 7(a), it is found that the strain at the adherent increased with the load, and the load stopped rising, when the strain began to decrease and then the specimen failed. It is explained that the

Fig.7(a) Variations of strains at the joint in tensile test

Fig.7(b) Variations of strains at the joint in bending test

Fig.7(c) Variations of strains at the joint in torsional test

decrease of the strain at the adherent was caused by the attenuation of the stress concentration at the joint. It can be said that such decrease of the strain shows the state of the failure at the joint. On the other hand, the strain at the overlay was small and the failure at the joint was not known from variations in it. In Fig. 7(b), the result of the bending test is shown. In this case, the strain at the adherent increased with the load and then the failure occurred suddenly. The strain in the torsional test shown in Fig. 7(c) increased with the load. And in the combined bending and torsional test, the strain in the longitudinal direction and that in the direction of 45° varied in the same manner as that at the bending test and that at the torsional one, respectively.

B. AE measurements

The locations of AE signals are shown in Figs. 8(a)-(d). In these figures, abscissas are the location of AE signals and ordinates are the AE event counts. The letters a and b on the abscissa corresponds to the ends of the overlay. In Fig. 8(a) showing the result of the tensile test, AE counts were uniformly distributed all over the location measured. In the bending test (Fig. 8(b)), more AE counts existed in the central part of the joint. On the other hand, in the torsional test (Fig. 8(d)), more AE counts existed near the ends of the joint. The result of the combined bending and torsional test in which the ratio of the bending moment to the torsional one is 1:1 is shown in Fig. 8(c). In this case, AE counts were distributed intermediately between that in the bending test and that in the torsional one.

From the above mentioned matter, the followings were known. The joint was uniformly damaged in the tensile test. The damaged area in the joint changed with the variation of the ratio of the bending moment to the torsional one. The higher the ratio of the bending moment to the torsional one was, the more AE counts in the central part were. And the higher the ratio of the torsional moment was, the more AE counts near the end of the joint were.

Fig.8(a) Location of AE sources in tensile test

Fig.8(b) Location of AE sources in bending test

Fig.8(c) Location of AE sources in combined bending and torsional test (bending moment : torsional moment = 1:1)

Fig.8(d) location of AE sources in torsional test

In Figs. 9(a)-(d) the AE amplitude distributions in each test are shown. More AE counts of AE signals having the low amplitude were observed in the tensile test as shown in Fig. 9(a). In the bending test (Fig. 9(b)), more AE counts were distributed in the high amplitude than that in the tensile test. And in the torsional test (Fig. 9(c)), the AE counts were uniformly distributed all over the amplitude measured. Almost the same AE amplitude distributions were observed in the combined load test in which the ratio of the bending moment to the torsional one was 1:1. (Fig. 9(d)) These experimental results are expected to be explained as followings. In the tensile test, the failure in the joint was mainly that of the adhesive and the adherent was not damaged. Therefore, AE signals having the lower amplitude were generated. On the other hand, in the bending, the torsional and the combined load tests, the adherent was damaged. Consequently, more AE signals having the higher amplitude were generated.

Fig.9(a) AE amplitude in tensile test

Fig.9(b) AE amplitude in bending test

Fig.9(c) AE amplitude in torsional test

Fig.9(d) AE amplitude in combined bending and torsional test (bending moment : torsional moment = 1:1)

The AE counts with the loading time in the tensile, the bending, the combined load and the torsional test are shown in Figs. 10(a)-(d). The abscissa is the loading time and the ordinate is the AE event counts. In the tensile test, the AE counts made little change with the loading time. On the other hand, in the bending, the torsional and the combined load test, the AE counts increased with the loading time. These results are explained as follows. In the tensile test, the damage occurred mainly in the adhesive layer and was limited only within it. Therefore, the AE counts kept the almost equal value with the loading time. On the other hand, the damage developed in the adherent with the load increased. Consequently, the AE counts increased as the damage developed in the adherent in other tests than tensile one.

CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical behaviors of GFRP cylindrical adhesively bonded joints were studied in the tensile, the bending, the torsional and the combined bending and torsional tests. In each test, the strain and the AE signals at the joint were measured, and the failure processes at the joint were examined. Consequently, the followings became clear.

- (1) The failure criterion of GFRP cylindrical adhesively bonded joints under the combined bending and torsional load was expressed by the elliptic equation.
- (2) From the results of the strain and the AE measurements, it was known that the failure at the joint occurred mainly in the adhesive layer under the tensile load, but under the combined load the delamination of the surface layer of the adherent occurred and then failed.
- (3) The failure area at the joint was changed in accordance with the loading condition. Under the bending load, the damage mainly occurred at the central part of the joint, and when the ratio of the torsional moment under the combined load became higher, the main damaged area shifted from the center part to the area near the end of the joint.

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Fig.10 AE-time characteristics
 (a)in tensile test,(b)in bending test,
 (c)in combined bending and torsional test
 (bending moment : torsional moment = 1:1),
 (d)in torsional test